

Modelling Oscar Peterson's Improvisation in 'Georgia On My Mind' Using Markov Chains

By Shaurya Gupta – June 2025

1.	<i>Abstract</i>	3
2.	<i>Introduction</i>	4
3.	<i>Methodology</i>	5
4.	<i>Analysis</i>	6
5.	<i>Discussion</i>	13
6.	<i>Conclusions</i>	14
7.	<i>References</i>	15

1. Abstract

For this research paper, I will be using Oscar Peterson's 'Georgia On My Mind' as my case study. This piece perfectly showcases Peterson's famous stylistic features and brings out some of the most intricate details in his work.

In this paper, I am going to use the Markov Chain, which uses mathematical concepts and principles, to analyse Peterson's virtuosic improvisations and display his unpredictable modulations as something more deliberate and planned using transition probability.

I will display this data in two key ways: transition probability heatmaps and Markov Chain transition graphs. These mathematical models will reflect both melodic and harmonic movement, allowing us to understand Peterson's improvisation logic. These models will also allow us to draw conclusions about Peterson's signature stylistic features that he includes in his improvisation by allowing us to spot common melodic patterns over specific chords.

2. Introduction

Oscar Peterson was one of the greatest jazz pianists and was born in 1925 in Montreal and passed away in 2007. He is undoubtedly one of the most influential jazz musicians of all time because of his expressive improvisations and incredible technical ability.

The jazz impresario Norma Granz invited Peterson to Carnegie Hall in New York where his international career began. After that, Peterson toured the world with the Philharmonic ensemble. Art Tatum and Nat King Cole were his greatest role models and had the most significant impact on him – he set up a guitar, bass and piano trio that exactly replicated Cole's group.

Peterson's style was composed of his fast, virtuosic right-hand runs accompanied by a strong swing feel. He focused on solo and duet performances in the 1970s and collaborated with Niels-Henning Ørsted Pedersen for his duets. Peterson went on to win eight Grammy Awards and he also won the Praemium Imperiale in 1999.

3. Methodology

For this project, I will be using a harmonic contextual Markov chain. Markov chains are mathematical models that capture the probability of moving from one musical element to another; in the case of Georgia On My Mind, I have chosen to use each note in context with its chord as the musical element. There are many benefits of choosing to record the harmonic context of each note rather than only recording the note which includes being able to simultaneously analyse harmonic patterns and how it influences the melodic line.

I have chosen to analyse bars 9-24 and I will attach the transcript of these bars in the next section. The key reason for choosing a segment of this length is that it is long enough to present patterns and allow us to capture key melodic ideas and chord transitions. It also contains a variety of harmonic patterns and cycles including a I-vi-ii-V progression.

Markov chain allows us to reveal hidden structures in a performer's improvisations which can seem spontaneous to the ear but is often based on consistent patterns. To build this Markov chain, I will first write each note along with its chord in order in a list. Recording accidentals is crucial to preserve accuracy and ultimately lead to more reliable patterns and a more precise conclusion. Once each note has been transcribed, a transition matrix is built that records the frequency and probability of changes in each element. I will then visualize this matrix using a heatmap and a Markov graph.

4. Analysis

Transcription extract:

The first system of the transcription extract consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and contains a melodic line with a wavy line above it, indicating a vibrato effect. It features a quintuplet of eighth notes, followed by a triplet of eighth notes, and then a triplet of quarter notes. The lower staff is in bass clef and provides harmonic support with chords and single notes. Above the system, the chords $Dm7^b5$, $Cm7$, and $F7$ are indicated.

The second system of the transcription extract consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line with a triplet of eighth notes, a quintuplet of eighth notes, and another triplet of eighth notes. The lower staff provides harmonic support with chords and single notes. Above the system, the chords $Bb7$, $Eb7$, $C7$, and $F7$ are indicated. A dashed line labeled "8va" is positioned above the right side of the upper staff.

The third system of the transcription extract consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a *loco* marking and contains a complex melodic line with a quintuplet of eighth notes, a triplet of eighth notes, and a sextuplet of eighth notes. The lower staff provides harmonic support with chords and single notes. Above the system, the chords $Bb7$ and $Eb7$ are indicated.

The fourth system of the transcription extract consists of two staves. The upper staff contains a melodic line with a triplet of eighth notes and a triplet of quarter notes. The lower staff provides harmonic support with chords and single notes. Above the system, the chords $Abmaj9$, $Gm7$, and $C7$ are indicated.

The fifth system of the transcription extract consists of two staves. The upper staff contains a melodic line with a triplet of eighth notes, a triplet of eighth notes, and a triplet of quarter notes. The lower staff provides harmonic support with chords and single notes. Above the system, the chords $Fm7$, $Ebm7$, $Dm7$, and $Dbm7$ are indicated.

Cm7 F7 Bb7 Eb7

Musical notation for the first system, featuring Cm7, F7, Bb7, and Eb7 chords. The right hand has a melodic line with triplets and a quintuplet. The left hand has a bass line with triplets.

Ab7 Db7 Ab7 G7 C7

Musical notation for the second system, featuring Ab7, Db7, Ab7, G7, and C7 chords. The right hand has a melodic line with triplets and a sextuplet. The left hand has a bass line with triplets.

Fm7 G7 C7 Fm7 Db7 C7

Musical notation for the third system, featuring Fm7, G7, C7, Fm7, Db7, and C7 chords. The right hand has a melodic line with triplets. The left hand has a bass line with triplets.

Fm7 G7 C7

Musical notation for the fourth system, featuring Fm7, G7, and C7 chords. The right hand has a melodic line with a triplet. The left hand has a bass line.

Markov Chain:

('Dmin7', 'Ab'), ('Dmin7', 'Bb'), ('Dmin7', 'Ab'), ('Dmin7', 'F'),
 ('Dmin7', 'Ab'), ('Dmin7', 'Bb'), ('Cmin7', 'C'), ('Cmin7', 'Eb'),
 ('Cmin7', 'C'), ('Cmin7', 'Eb'), ('Fmaj7', 'C'),
 ('Bbmaj7', 'C'), ('Bbmaj7', 'Db'), ('Bbmaj7', 'F'), ('Ebmin7', 'A'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'C'), ('Ebmin7', 'A'), ('Ebmin7', 'Bb'), ('Ebmin7', 'C'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'Db'), ('Ebmin7', 'F'), ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'C'), ('Ebmin7', 'Eb'), ('Ebmin7', 'F'), ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'),
 ('Cmaj7', 'C'), ('Fmaj7', 'F'), ('Bbmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Bbmaj7', 'B'),
 ('Bbmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Bbmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Bbmaj7', 'Db'),
 ('Bbmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Bbmaj7', 'Eb'), ('Bbmaj7', 'Db'), ('Bbmaj7', 'D'),
 ('Bbmaj7', 'Db'), ('Bbmaj7', 'D'), ('Ebmin7', 'Db'), ('Ebmin7', 'D'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'Db'), ('Ebmin7', 'B'), ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'Bb'), ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'), ('Ebmin7', 'Eb'), ('Ebmin7', 'F'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'), ('Ebmin7', 'Bb'), ('Ebmin7', 'C'), ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'Eb'), ('Ebmin7', 'D'), ('Ebmin7', 'Db'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'Eb'), ('Ebmin7', 'C'), ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'), ('Ebmin7', 'F'),
 ('Abmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Abmaj7', 'C'), ('Abmaj7', 'Eb'), ('Abmaj7', 'C'),
 ('Abmaj7', 'D'), ('Abmaj7', 'F'), ('Abmaj7', 'A'),
 ('Gmaj7', 'C'), ('Gmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Gmaj7', 'Db'), ('Gmaj7', 'Eb'),
 ('Cmaj7', 'Gb'), ('Cmaj7', 'Db'), ('Cmaj7', 'Eb'), ('Fmaj7', 'F'),
 ('Fmaj7', 'C'), ('Ebmin7', 'F'), ('Ebmin7', 'Eb'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'C'), ('Ebmin7', 'F'), ('Dmin7', 'Ab'), ('Cmin7', 'Ab'),
 ('Cmin7', 'Bb'), ('Cmin7', 'C'), ('Cmin7', 'Eb'), ('Fmaj7', 'G'),
 ('Fmaj7', 'F'), ('Bbmaj7', 'Db'), ('Bbmaj7', 'F'),
 ('Bbmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Ebmin7', 'C'), ('Ebmin7', 'Eb'), ('Ebmin7', 'C'),
 ('Ebmin7', 'Eb'), ('Ebmin7', 'F'), ('Ebmin7', 'Ab'), ('Ebmin7', 'Bb'),
 ('Abmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Abmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Abmaj7', 'B'),
 ('Abmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Abmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Abmaj7', 'F'), ('Abmaj7', 'Eb'),
 ('Abmaj7', 'Db'), ('Abmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Abmaj7', 'Eb'), ('Abmaj7', 'Db'),
 ('Abmaj7', 'Eb'), ('Abmaj7', 'B'), ('Abmaj7', 'C'),
 ('Abmaj7', 'Ab'), ('Gmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Gmaj7', 'Db'), ('Cmaj7', 'Ab'),
 ('Cmaj7', 'E'), ('Cmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Fmin7', 'C'), ('Fmin7', 'F'),
 ('Fmin7', 'Ab'), ('Gmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Cmaj7', 'Ab'),
 ('Cmaj7', 'C'), ('Fmin7', 'Ab'), ('Fmin7', 'F'), ('Fmin7', 'G'),
 ('Fmin7', 'F'), ('Fmin7', 'E'), ('Fmin7', 'F'), ('Dbmaj7', 'Ab'),
 ('Cmaj7', 'C'), ('Fmin7', 'Ab'), ('Gmaj7', 'Bb'), ('Cmaj7', 'E'), ('Cmaj7', 'C')

Figure 1 - Extracted Markov Chain (Bars 9–24 of Georgia on My Mind)

Figure 1 shows the Markov chain which has been generated from bars 9-24 of Georgia On My Mind. Each segment in the sequence is composed of the chord and the note which the chord has been played in. This sequence has been created in chronological order from first to last note.

Figure 2 represents the transition matrix generated using the data from figure 1 – the Markov chain. The rows in the matrix represent the current state and the columns represent the next state. Each cell represents the probability that the row state will transition to the column state. For example, if a row cell contains Ab and a column cell contains Bb and the cell's value is 0.4, there is a 40% chance that if the note Ab has just been played, the next note will be Bb. This means that each row will sum to 1.0.

Markov Transition Matrix Heatmaps

Figure 4 - Transition Matrix Heatmap

Figure 4 shows the Markov transition matrix represented as a heatmap. In this heatmap, a gradient of colours is used to represent different probabilities. On the x-axis and y-axis, all the possible states are shown in order of ascending scale. The y-axis represents the current state, and the x-axis represents the next state. Each cell in the matrix is filled with the colour that represents the probability of the state corresponding to the y-axis value of that cell moving to the state corresponding to the x-axis value of that cell.

For example, if we choose the current state to be Gmaj7: C then we know that Oscar Peterson is guaranteed to transition to Gmaj7: Bb because it is the only cell coloured yellow, and this means it has a 1.0 chance of occurring.

It can also be noticed that each row must add up to 1.0 for the transition matrix to hold true.

5. Discussion

There are three key parts of Peterson's improvisation that this Markov analysis can provide: predictability, style and technique.

In the transition matrix heatmap, the most noticeable pattern is negative linear pattern from top left to top right. Since the axes are arranged sequentially, this shows that Peterson favours small steps from state to state rather than large leaps. He avoids jumping between distance tonal regions and prefers to stay in the same regions. He frequently transitions to neighbouring notes indicating a melodic and smooth phrasing style rather than angular leaps. The key feature of Peterson's improvisation that this pattern unveils is his predictable unpredictability. While the notes may seem random to the ear, we can see that these steps are measured and always correlate to this negative linear pattern.

Furthermore, Peterson's ability to balance melodic intent and harmonic stability across this large range of highlights his mastery of the keyboard in which he is comfortable in any musical state.

Peterson tends to emphasize particular chord: note combinations like Ebmin7: F which are harmonically safe states to be in as they represent chord extensions like the root, 3rd, 5th, 7th, 9th, etc. In the case of Ebmin7: F, the note is the 9th of the chord which gives Peterson a harmonically stable state to move to.

From the Markov chain network graph, the dense cluster of nodes on the right-hand side of the graph shows how Peterson favours moving to particular states like Ebmaj7: Ab or Bbmaj7: Db showing his preference for particular harmonic colours and tensions.

Some of the coloured cells scattered more sparsely around the negative linear pattern in the Markov transition matrix heatmap show his tendency to explore more unexpected states from time to time whilst balancing this with his more predictable structure shown by the linear correlation. These occasional adventurous state transitions add colour without losing coherence or structure.

6. Conclusions

This Markov chain analysis of Oscar Peterson's solo in Georgia on My Mind used mathematical models to reveal and visualise consistent transitions, reflecting a style built on structure and colour. The resulting unpredictability, within a structured probability model, highlights both his technical range and musical creativity.

Even though Peterson's improvisations may seem random and unpredictable at first, after analysing his work we can conclude that his improvisations are melodically smooth with usually small steps and occasional adventurous leaps to add colour, but his improvisations are grounded in favoured chord: note pairs and transition patters.

To further improve findings, building a Markov chain using a larger transcription would help improve the reliability of this analysis and building Markov chains of other Oscar Peterson improvisations can be used to compare whether these patterns are consistent across his works implying it is a feature of his style or if this analysis only applies to this extract of improvisation.

7. References

Encyclopaedia Britannica. (n.d.). *Oscar Peterson | Jazz Pianist, Composer, Arranger*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Oscar-Peterson> (Accessed: 27 June 2025).

Peterson, O. (n.d.). *Georgia on My Mind* [PDF transcription]. Unpublished. Available from local archive.

Author note:

I wrote this paper independently as part of a personal research project exploring the intersection of jazz improvisation and mathematical modelling. I am a secondary school student interested in mathematics, economics and music.